

Cobalt containing Cerium Oxide as a Multifunctional Nanocatalyst for various Selective organic transformations

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Abstract:

The development of a multifunctional nanocatalyst for industrially relevant selective organic transformations is highly needed for the sustainable future of chemical industries. Cobalt containing cerium oxide nanocatalyst (MPCo@CeO₂NC) was prepared via simple coprecipitation method. The characterization of MPCo@CeO₂NC was carried out using different physiochemical techniques such as PXRD, FE-SEM, HR-TEM, EDAX-mapping, TGA, BET, and XPS analysis. The structural characterizations such as XRD and XPS analysis discovered the presence of the mixed phase of cobalt such as cobalt and cobalt oxide present in MPCo@CeO₂NC. Based on sustainability various industrially relevant organic transformations such as (i) nitrile formation from aldehyde, (ii) aldehydes to form tertiary *N,N*-dimethyl amines, and (iii) direct acetylation of alcohols/amines were achieved in an excellent manner using MPCo@CeO₂NC as the multifunctional catalyst. Our catalyst showed superior substrates scope with excellent yield for each type of reaction and recyclability.

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